

**“Time” in Quantum Mechanics and Relativity –
Spatial Arithmetic explain What “time” is?**

In quantum mechanics, time is a parameter. However, according to the Theory of Relativity, time is a fourth dimension of space, which is warped (“expanded”) as an object moves.

Both theories are not wrong, but they both describe time inaccurately.

In reality, time doesn't inherently exist; it's created when space is formed. As we see, when an object moves, creating space for a stationary system, it also causes the time of the stationary system to slow down (or increase). This reflects that time is the variation of space (space – the spatial value created by the energy of motion).

Don't be confused about apparent space. Here, space needs to be understood from the perspective of spatial value (created space).

For example, an object moves from A to B (the segment AB is 1m long) and then returns to A. The space created at this point is 2m (not the apparent space of the 1m segment AB). This is also the time created. The confusion here stems from our choice of different units of measurement for time and space, leading us to mistakenly believe that time and space are different dimensions. In reality, they are essentially one; the units of measurement for days, months, years, hours, minutes, and seconds are merely creations of humanity.

Furthermore, the perception of time is due to the expansion of the universe, causing space to increase (time to flow). When an object is not moving, we still feel time flowing because space is being created (the universe is expanding). If we completely separate the frame of reference, there would be no created space, and therefore no time.

To clarify this issue further, let's consider the formula for calculating the time elasticity of two reference frames, one stationary (time t) and one moving (time t').

We have: $(t')^2 = (1 - v^2 / c^2) \cdot t^2$

$$\Leftrightarrow t^2 - (t')^2 = (v^2 / c^2) \cdot t^2$$

(When there is t , it means we are considering the reference frames in the variation of the total spatial value of the entire universe, $t^2 - (t')^2$ is the difference in the variation of the total spatial value of the entire universe between the stationary system and the moving system)

$$\Leftrightarrow t^2 - (t')^2 = (v^2 / c^2) \cdot t^2$$

$$\Leftrightarrow k_t S v = (v^2 \cdot t^2) / c^2 = s^2 / c^2 = k_s S v / c^2$$

(s is the distance – the space created, Sv is the spatial value created from the moving energy, because the system is placed within the variation of the total spatial value of the entire universe, this spatial value has a time slip coefficient k_t and a space slip coefficient k_s creating the spatial and temporal changes that we "see", with $k_t = k_s / c^2$).

Why is there a difference in the slip coefficient between space and time? Because time is also space, but we are considering it within the context of the changing space of the entire universe, whereas space when an object is in motion is only one dimension following the object's movement. When we consider the element of time, we are actually considering the system within the total variation of space created throughout the universe.

Therefore, if not placed within the context of the entire universe (without the t as previously understood), then time is essentially space.

Thus, time is essentially space created throughout the universe. Because we don't fully understand the nature of time, we view it as a fourth dimension of space (Relativity Theory) and thus separate time and space. For this reason, in the formula above, the value of space is calculated as the square of time or distance. We use a different unit of measurement for time than for space because we don't fully understand the nature of time, and using such a unit of measurement makes it easier for us to perform measurements and calculations.

For many years, humanity has misunderstood spacetime, while the true nature of spacetime is:

1. Spacetime is not a background field (spacetime is not curved as described by the Theory of Relativity); the essence of spacetime is the spatial value (space) generated by kinetic energy.

2. Time is not the fourth dimension of space and is not independent of space; time is space itself. Time is the variation of the spatial value of the entire universe (space is created when the universe expands). Misconceptions arose, and humanity viewed time as the fourth dimension and used different scales and units of measurement.

3. When considering a frame of reference with time, we are placing it within the context of the changing total spatial value of the entire universe. That is, they are not independent but are placed within the context of the changing spatial value of the entire universe (the universe is expanding – space is being created). This causes each frame of reference to have a different time. Therefore, the spatial value created by the energy of motion has a slip coefficient with $k_t = k_s / c^2$ (k_t is the time slip coefficient – called time but actually a slip coefficient relative to the change in the spatial value of the entire universe, k_s is the space slip coefficient, a slip coefficient that only compares one direction of energy motion – the distance being calculated).

This is only a personal viewpoint that I would like to share from my own reflections. Thank you for reading these lines.